

Land, Livestock and Conflict: An Assessment of Land Use Dynamics and Vegetal Resource Degradation in Nigeria's Agrarian Crises; the example of the Niger-Benue Trough

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Abstract

Nigeria's Benue Valley region has witnessed escalating farmer-pastoralist conflicts in recent years, primarily fueled by competition over land and water resources. This study investigates the role of land use/land cover changes (LULC), particularly vegetal resources as a primary driver of these conflicts. Utilizing Landsat satellite imagery, LULC changes were analyzed for a period spanning 30 years, examining 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020. Results reveal alarming degradation trends: grazing land decreased by 54.86% and arable land by 44.53%. On the other hand, grasslands increased by 107.54% and bare lands by 549.8%. These changes exacerbate drought and desertification, forcing pastoralists to migrate southward, and leading to violent conflicts. Further, climate change and Nigeria's growing population exacerbate competition for resources. This study underscores the urgent need for sustainable land management practices. The recommendations aimed at reducing these conflicts and promoting sustainable land use practices include: development of ranches and grazing reserves, revisiting symbiotic participatory conflict resolution approaches, massive afforestation and reforestation projects as well as proactive government oversight and support.

Keywords: Land Use Dynamics, Climate Change, Farmers-Pastoralists, Conflict, Nigeri

Introduction

Nigeria's agricultural productivity has been threatened over the years by several factors, including the use of crude implements, the land tenure system, poverty, government neglect, poor transportation and storage facilities, and more recently, insecurity in diverse forms, chief among them being the farmer-pastoralist conflicts (Okoli & Ogayi, 2018). Though widespread, this conflict has its hotbed in the Benue Valley region. Ilo *et al.* (2019) estimate that 10,000 lives were lost

to the conflict within a decade. The conflict has evolved from spontaneous reactions to provocations and now to deadlier planned attacks, particularly in Benue, Plateau, Adamawa, Nasarawa, and Taraba states. As at 2018, the conflict was already six times deadlier than Boko Haram's insurgency (International Crisis Group, 2018). Eje *et al.* (2017) pointed out that the conflict has demonstrated high potential to exacerbate insecurity and food crises, particularly in rural communities where most conflicts are

localized, with reverberating consequences nationwide. Farmer-pastoralist conflicts in Nigeria has persisted and stands as a serious threat to national food security, livestock production, and eradication of poverty, with farmers often regarded as the most vulnerable (Dimelu *et al.*, 2016).

Climate change which is the change in the state of the climate that can be identified by changes in the mean or the variability of its properties, and that persists for an extended period typically decades or longer (IPCC, 2007), has been linked to this conflict (Odjugo 2008; Shettima & Tar, 2008; Muniruzzaman, 2011; Maystadt, Calderon & You, 2014; Idowu 2018). The impact of climate change is increasingly pinpointed as one of the most serious security threats of the future and a far greater threat to the world's stability than international terrorism. Horste and Vlassenroot (2009) argue that climate change poses a risk to the reshaping of the productive landscape, exacerbating food, water, and energy scarcities, contributing to destabilization, and unregulated population movements and tension.

Most of these climate-related disasters such as droughts, desertification, land degradation etc. have underlying causes; they are sudden manifestations of slow but continuous processes (UNEP/GRID-Arendal, 2005). Climate change processes lead to changes in the land surface vegetation, water resources, soil, and atmosphere, which are the basic constituent elements that support life on earth. These changes are driven by a combination of both natural and anthropogenic causes. The effects of man's activities on climate variation was perceived before now as negligible, and so climate was generally taken for granted and there was little thought that the climate could cause problems with devastating effects (Brown and Crawford, 2008).

Adisa (2012) noted that the socio-economic lives of both the farmers and the pastoralists within a particular geographical setting revolve around land. Therefore, competition between crop farmers and animal pastoralists over access and control of fertile land, brought about by climate change becomes inevitable, easily degenerating into violent conflicts. Blench (2010) added that, struggles over the control and ownership of economically viable land cause more tension and violent conflicts among communities.

In the northern and middle belts of the country, the cereal-productive Sudan savannah ecology is transitioning into pure Sahel and the influence of the Sahara is increasing southwards. In the same vein, the root and tuber productive ecology of the Guinea savannah is giving way to Sudan savannah grassland. The predominant Fulani herdsmen of the lower Sahel and Sudan savannah ecologies are now moving south - to the Guinea savannah and Forest belt of the South - to find greener pasture for their herds (Adogi, 2013). This is unacceptable to the root and tuber farmers of the Guinea Savannah who are already farming close to the climatic margin of cultivation. With the fear that the Fulani herdsmen will destroy their farmlands, the natural result is clashes over rights to the lands.

This movement of the pastoralists must be understood as a consequence of the global trend of climate change (Blench, 2003). In his seminal work on natural resource conflict in north-central Nigeria, Blench (2004) sought to establish the nexus between pastoral migration and increased herder/farmer conflicts in the ecological zone that also encompasses the Benue Valley. It was noted that, climate change, desertification and drought, land tenure and scarcity, as well as pastoral migration are the major factors that account for the spiralling farmer/herder conflict in the region. This corroborates the

dominant scholarly standpoint on the subject matter, as we have seen in the foregoing.

This conflict has also constituted severe threat to the means of survival and livelihoods of both farmers and herdsman. Dimelu *et al.* (2017) stressed that it is a formidable challenge to economic development, and a threat to food security and sustainable livelihood of the agrarian communities. The implication is that the conflicts give rise to insecurity, displacement, disability and death, poor food production, and widespread hunger and malnutrition.

This study is interested in examining and assessing the intricate relationship between changes in land use and the conflict between farmers and pastoralists in the Benue Valley region with a view to providing empirical explanation for the factors affecting natural resource depletion and uses which has resulted to the prevailing conflict in the region.

Methods

The Study Area

The Benue Valley which is located in central Nigeria and is a part of the Niger-Benue Trough is an extensive area bordering the River Benue, from which it derives its name. It is considered to have originated as an aulacogen on the Precambrian shield as a result of the separation of the African and American plates in early Cretaceous times (Ogungbesan & Akaegbobi, 2011). Located between longitude 6°38' and 10°53' East of the Greenwich meridian and from latitude 6°31' and 9° 26' North of the equator, covering all of Benue State and parts of Kogi, Taraba, Nasarawa and Plateau states, it is bordered to the west by the River Niger; Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi, and Cross River states to the south; the Republic of Cameroun in the south east, Taraba State to the west; and Nasarawa and Plateau states to the north.

The climate of the region is of mild tropical continental with two distinct seasons (i.e. tropical wet and dry) with the designation Aw in the Koppens and Geiger climate classification. The dry season starts from late November to March and wet season prevails from April to October. The wet season is characterized by the tropical maritime air mass which brings rainfall and wet conditions to the region. It has a hot atmospheric condition with temperatures generally over 30⁰c, as warm air drains down the valley and remains stagnant with little wind and reduced precipitation in the absence of highlands to intercept the rain-bearing winds (Mage & Tyubee, 2017). The Benue Valley region is an extensive lowland area generally below 300 metres and drained by the River Benue and its major tributaries: River Katsina-Ala and River Gongola (Britannica.com, 2011).

Agriculture is a major means of livelihood in the region however, fishing activities are common among the Jukuns and other tribes along the riverine areas. Commercial fishing activities are carried out in River Benue and its major tributaries where different fresh water fish species are caught and sold.

The major land use types in the region are residential, arable lands, tree crops, fallow plots, open grazing lands and forests. Like most parts of the country, communal land ownership, individual land tenure, freehold, inheritance tenure and rentals are the dominant land ownership systems in the region (Idoma & Ismai'l, 2014). Okoli & Atelhe (2014) assert that the conflict over resources in this area is primarily due to the major economic activity of the people. The farmers who are the majority continue to expand areas cultivated thereby edging out the pastoralists. With limited access to land and water resources, the pastoralists fight back and the result is what we have experienced in the region in the last 15 years.

Data Collection

Imagery used for the study area was obtained from Landsat. Images were exported to ArcGIS 10.2, geo-referenced, and subsequently used to determine the land use/land cover change (LULC). LULC has two separate terminologies that are often used interchangeably (Rawat & Kumar 2015). Land cover refers to the biophysical characteristics of the earth's surface, including the distribution of vegetation, water, soil, and other physical features of the land. While land use refers to the way land has been used by humans and their habitats, usually with an emphasis on the functional role of land for economic activities.

This study employed satellite remote-sensing images of Nigeria spanning three decades, with a resolution of 30m, from which images of the Benue Valley region were extracted. Satellite imagery were used to classify the land use and land cover (LULC) for 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020. The images were from the global land survey collection of Landsat

5, Thematic Mapper (TM), Landsat 7, Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM), Landsat 8, and Operational Land Imager (OLI) (Table 1.0). The satellite imageries were obtained from <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>. They were used to detect changes in land use, vegetation and water, which are the basic farming and pastoral resources. The major land use considered were: undisturbed forests which are forests and woodlands with no known significant human intervention; Savanna woodland which are areas with higher tree populations; grasslands which are savannah areas dominated by grasses; arable lands which are areas capable of being ploughed and suitable for growing crops; orchards which are intentional plantation of trees or trees maintained for food production e.g. mango; livestock projects like grazing land/reserve, and waterbody which are accumulation of water on the surface such as rivers and lakes, and bare land which are areas with no dominant vegetation etc.

Table 1.0 Details of Images Used for Land Use/Land Cover Change

Date acquired	Satellite	Sensor	Number of Band	Spatial Resolution	Format
24-11-1990	Landsat 5	TM	7	Bands 1-5,7: 30x30 Band 6: 60x60	Geotiff
19-01-2000	Landsat 7	ETM	8	Bands 1-5,7: 30x30 Band 6: 60x60	Geotiff
03-02-2010	Landsat 7	ETM+	8	Bands 1-5,7: 30x30 Band 6: 60x60	Geotiff
17-12-2020	Landsat 8	OLI	11	Bands 2-7: 30x30 Bands 10: 100x100	Geotiff

2.3 Methods

Images were exported to ArcGIS 10.2 and georeferenced, and with the help of the maximum likelihood method, classification was carried out on the images. The post-classification comparison technique of change detection algorithms was used because it minimizes sensor, atmospheric and environmental differences and provides a complete matrix of land cover change when using multiple images (Teng et al., 2008). Precision testing was conducted using the Kappa index and the overall accuracy for classification (Barasa et al., 2020; Keshtkar et al., 2017).

(a) imagery pre-processing

In the study, Landsat TM imagery was used for the 1990 data, ETM for 2000 and 2010, and OLI_TIRS (Operational Land Imager/Thermal Infrared Sensor) image was employed for 2020. All images were pre-processed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) National Center for Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) to correct radiometric and geometrical distortions to level 1G products. All the bands were utilized at a spatial resolution of 30m. These spectral bands were layer-stacked to produce a composite image of the study area for each year (1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020) for the purpose of land use/land cover classification and image analysis.

(b) image geo-referencing

The datasets were georeferenced or geo-rectified (registration) to a geographic coordinate system. The images were imported into Erdas Imagine 9.2 environment where they were rectified to a common projection (Universal Traverse Mercator). According to Spellman (2011), the UTM projection unlike the Geographic Coordinate System (latitude/longitude) is more reliable since its measurements are cited in linear, decimal units, rather than in angular, non-decimal units. This was done to translate the

images' real world coordinates to digital format so that they can be matched with other relevant and related maps used in this study. Geo-referencing which involves registering data to the real world was carried out by assigning geographic information like location and position, to the data sets (images). This helped in defining the existence of those datasets in a physical space as well as establish their location in the real world.

(c) image sub-setting

For sub-setting, Landsat TM imagery was used for 1990, ETM for 2000 and 2010, and Landsat 8 imagery for 2020, with a 30m spatial resolution. Since the satellite imageries are in bands and cover larger areas, with the Erdas Imagine 9.2 software, the area of interest (the study area) was subset from the overall imagery for each year under consideration.

(d) image classification

In classifying the images, the supervised classification technique was employed using maximum likelihood classification (MLC) algorithm. This technique enabled generation of training classes based on the actual land-use/land-cover themes present within the study area and helped in avoiding the ambiguity that is typically associated with the unsupervised technique of image classification (Liu *et al.*, 2002). The MLC is the most commonly used with remotely-sensed data, and is proven to yield the best classification result (Jensen, 1996). The attributes and statistics generated from the classification were used for post-classification comparison between the years (Chunwate *et al.*, 2019).

Based on prior knowledge of the area and reconnaissance survey, a classification scheme after Anderson, et al. (1976) was adopted for this study. The classification scheme has been modified to present undisturbed forest, orchards, Savannah

woodland, grassland, arable land, grazing land, bare land and water body.

Results

The LULC classification maps of years 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020 produced in this study are displayed in Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. Each of the maps shows the 8 classes of land use considered in this study: undisturbed forest, orchards, savannah woodland, grassland, arable land, grazing land, bare land, and waterbody in the study area. The overall accuracy of LULC classification was 89.76% in 1990, 91.64.50% in 1990, 88.09% in 2010, and 91.72% in 2020. Anderson (1976) specifies that the minimum acceptable standard of overall accuracy assessment should be $\geq 85\%$, as specified by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) classification scheme. In other words, results of accuracy assessment of classified images will be unreliable if

overall accuracy is less than 85%. The overall accuracies for all the selected images in this study meet this standard criterion.

The temporal changes show the areal coverage and proportion of the 8 LULC classes for each year (1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020) as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Temporal Changes of the Landuse/Landcover

Landuse/ Landcover	Area in Km ²								30 years % Change
	1990	%	2000	%	2010	%	2020	%	
Undisturbed Forest	3946.56	4.86	3271.66	4.03	3011.63	3.71	2022.45	2.49	-48.77
Orchards	18248.64	22.46	17747.82	21.84	16705.9	20.56	16111.42	19.83	-11.71
Savannah Woodland	19001.22	23.38	18117.82	22.29	9372.74	11.53	8477.78	10.43	-55.39
Grassland	13467.57	16.57	12983.8	15.98	28157.09	34.65	27945.03	34.39	+107.54
Arable Land	19003.33	23.38	18842.54	23.19	11999.98	14.77	10544.33	12.97	-44.53
Grazing Land	4677.22	5.76	3387.6	4.17	2311.81	2.84	2111.43	2.60	-54.86
Bareland	2037.29	2.51	6073.51	7.47	8701.52	10.71	13253.51	16.31	+549.8
Waterbody	885.34	1.09	842.42	1.04	1006.5	1.24	801.22	0.99	-9.17
Total	81267.17	100	81267.17	100	81267.17	100	81267.17	100	

Source: Author's GIS Analysis, 2021

Fig. 1 showed the areal extent of the LULC classes in 1990. Arable land and savannah woodland have the highest percentage of 23.38% each while undisturbed forest was

scattered within the savannah woodland across the region. Orchards are a prominent feature within Benue State and parts of Kogi State, accounting for 22.46% of the entire

region. It can be noted that the north-eastern part of the region that is degraded (bareland) account for 2.51%, mainly around the

Langtang area in Plateau State. Grazing land is majorly in the upper north of River Benue

and south-eastern part of the region specifically in Taraba State. The grassland predominates the west of Kogi State and parts of Benue State.

Fig. 1: Landuse/Landcover Change Map of the Study Area in 1990

Fig. 2 shows the areal extent of the LULC classes in 2000. There is increasing vegetal degradation between 1990 and 2000. Bareland which existed only in Plateau before 1990 had expanded by 7.47% into northern parts of Nasarawa State with few patches in Taraba State and the northeastern

part of Benue State. This has led to a marked reduction in the areal extent of grasslands and orchards. On the other hand, arable land has the highest areal coverage with 23.19%.

Fig. 2: Landuse/Landcover Change Map of the Study Area in 2000

As shown in Fig. 3, the degradation trends upwards by 10.71%, becoming more prominent in the northern fringes of Benue State and western parts of Taraba State. However, the most significant observation

for 2010 is the exponential increase in grassland areal extent to 34.65%, thereby decimating the savannah woodland, undisturbed forest, and the grazing areas in southern Taraba.

Fig. 3: Landuse/Landcover Change Map of the Study Area in 2010

Fig. 4 indicates that the period running up to 2020 witnessed the most degradation as bare lands became evident in southeastern parts of Benue State. This led the increase in the areal

extent of bareland to 16.31%. Other land use types such as undisturbed forest, orchard, woodland, and arable land continue to show a steady decreasing trend.

Fig. 4: Landuse/Landcover Change Map of the Study Area in 2020

The Temporal Changes of the Landuse/Landcover

The processing and supervised classification of Landsat imagery (TM, ETM+, and OLI/TIRS) acquired for 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020 produced four classification maps for the eight LULC types prevalent in the study area. Significant changes in the LULC classes over the past 30 years (1990–2020) have been detected. In this period, bareland and grassland showed significant increase (positive changes) of over 549.8% and 107.54% respectively, within the period, an evidence of vegetal degradation. In the same period (1990–2020), the LULC classes that reduced significantly (negative changes) are grazing land (-54.86%), arable land (-44.53%), savannah woodland (-55.39%), orchards (-11.71%), and undisturbed forest (-

48.77%), representing a significant negative percentage change of 54.86%, 44.53%, 55.39%, 11.71% and 48.77% respectively. Most of these turned into grasslands or badlands.

Discussion

Okeleye *et al.* (2023) observed a similar trend in land use and land cover changes in North Central Nigeria between 1990 and 2020, and reported that most of the vegetation, agricultural land and water bodies in Kwara and Benue states have become barren lands and been converted to built-up areas. In another research, Ali *et al.* (2021) observed that bare lands/sandbars have the highest annual rate of change amongst the land cover they studied in Benue State over the same period of 1990 and 2020. These are signs of desertification and according to the United

Nations, in the past sixty years, it has affected approximately 350,000 square kilometers in Nigeria. It also reported that desertification continues towards the southern parts of the country at about 600 metres annually (Shehu, 2018). Additionally, Nugent (2018) noted that desertification presently affects as much as 60% of Nigeria's land while Uche (2020) holds that on the average, over 409,700 hectares of forest are lost in Nigeria annually, with evaporation rate rapidly increasing while aggregate rainfall has reduced by about 7-11% between 1990 and 2005, leading to warmer weather.

The impacts of desertification, deforestation, and environmental degradation have contributed to the migration of pastoralists from the northern fringe of the region, where such degradation was only evident as early as 1990. This movement has largely been southwards, driven by the scarcity of fodder and water created by these conditions, as pastoralists seek greener pastures within the valley. The continual advancing trend of vegetal degradation results in further pastoralist migration, often leading to violent conflicts between pastoralists and the farming communities on their paths (Okoli & Atelhe, 2014), who have also encroached on previous grazing routes and areas as they aimed for greater agricultural productivity.

The results of this study demonstrate that the effects of climate change such as environmental degradation and desertification, have increased bare lands and transformed forest and savannah woodlands into grasslands (Ayih, 2003; Ayuba, *et al.*, 2007; Odjugo, 2008; Babe *et al.*, 2012). The results also reveal a significant reduction in grazing land (-55%) and arable land (-45%) over the 30-year period (1990-2010). This situation

has engendered more southward migration by pastoralists, bringing them into direct conflicts with farming communities, both parties having been affected by the challenges arising from climate change. Resultantly, in its wake, these conflicts have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives, and the displacement of hundreds of thousands who have abandoned their homes and farmlands for over 7 to 10 years.

Conclusion

The result of the land use/land cover change over the 30-year period (1990-2010) showed positive changes for bare lands and grasslands, but a negative for grazing lands, arable lands, savannah woodlands, orchards, and undisturbed forests, depicting widespread vegetal degradation as a result of climate change. The impacts of desertification, deforestation, and environmental degradation have contributed to the migration of pastoralists from the northern fringe of the region, where such degradation was only evident as early as 1990. This movement has largely been southwards, driven by the scarcity of fodder and water created by these conditions, as pastoralists seek greener pastures within the valley, leading to violent conflicts between them and farming communities on their paths, who have also encroached on previous grazing routes.

In view of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The government should establish well-planned ranches and grazing reserves. This can be done in collaboration with traditional rulers, farming communities and the pastoralists through associations such as the Miyetti Allah Cattle Breeders Association (MACBAN).

- ii. The menace of farm encroachment on grazing areas can be minimized through

enforcement. This can go hand-in-hand with public enlightenment on the need to respect government laws on grazing reserves.

iii. Greater participation of indigenous resource user groups in the policy formulation process relating to natural resource management and utilization should be encouraged. This will ameliorate feelings of marginalization.

iv. The government, communities and individuals should embark on massive afforestation and reforestation programmes to reduce the impact of climate change.

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